

PRODUCT DATA FOR LIFE CYCLE SUPPORT

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the technical details of the Air Force Manufacturing Technology PDES Application Protocols for Electronics (PAP-E) program. This program is developing PDES (Product Data Exchange using STEP (STandard for the Exchange of Product model data)) application protocols, to be presented to the International Electrotechnical Committee (IEC) and International Standards Organization (ISO) STEP standards community. The application protocols to be developed by this program are for the representation of printed circuit assembly (PCA) and line replaceable module (LRM) test, diagnostics, and re-engineering life cycle support product data. In addition to the PDES/STEP standards focus, product data requirements in the form of information models are being provided to existing electronics product data standards bodies such as the IEEE, EIA, and CAD Framework Initiative, Inc. (CFI).

PRODUCT DATA BACKGROUND

Efforts to standardize product representation to support the unambiguous exchange of product data are beginning to center around the Product Data Exchange using STEP (STandard for the Exchange of Product model data) (PDES/STEP) initiative and its information model development approach. The goal of the PDES/STEP development effort is the establishment of an international standard for the representation and communication of a complete product definition for use throughout the product life-cycle (concept through disposal). The magnitude of the effort has resulted in a PDES/STEP structure of working committees that is broad in scope. Air Force investigations have revealed a need for the definition of application-specific portions of PDES/STEP to allow for near term implementation and to facilitate the validation of PDES/STEP for key applications. Figure 1 shows the overall scope of the PDES/STEP initiative with the electrical application area broken out. Within the electrical application area the focus views for the PAP-E program are highlighted. Figure 1 also shows the relationship between the PAP-E program and the PDES, Inc. Electrical/Electronics project. By focusing on the development, and demonstration of a set of application protocols for

electronics, the harmonization of current electronic data standards (e.g. VHSIC Hardware Description Language

(VHDL), Electronic Design Interchange Format (EDIF), and Initial Graphics Exchange Specification (IGES)) can also be accomplished. In addition, a demonstrated set of application protocols for electronics can be provided to the PDES/STEP community for standardization. Finally, the development and demonstration of information models, linked with current electronics data standards, can be provided to the electronics CAD and tester vendors as a means of facilitating better information sharing across diverse vendor environments and tools.

Figure 1. Scope of PDES/STEP Initiative

PAP-E Goals and Objectives

The Air Force has a wide variety of electronic components developed by many sources. The need for product data from these sources for the integration, test, repair, and re-engineering of these components, and/or subcomponents, is currently a critical problem. With the introduction of increased electronics complexity in systems, the aforementioned problem threatens to eliminate the Air Force's ability to support and efficiently modify its complex electronic systems. This project will define a functional model representing the development, capture, and utilization

of product data necessary for the life cycle support of electronic products. From this functional model a set of product data application protocols for test, integrated diagnostic, and re-engineering will be developed consistent with the PDES/STEP approach of information modeling.

These developed application protocols will represent the product information necessary and sufficient for the life cycle support of complex electronics, focused at the level of electronics integration represented by Line Replaceable Modules (LRM), Printed Wiring Assemblies (PWA), and Shop Replaceable Units (SRU). This project will therefore provide a representative set of complex application protocols for the electronics domain to be used by the PDES/STEP community for the verification and validation of the PDES/STEP electrical integrating resources and overall information model development approach to new product data standards. These application protocols may also be used as a representative set of information necessary for submission to the Department of Defense, or other customer, by an electronics product vendor. The models may, in addition, be used for the definition of the information which should be maintained by original electronics component manufacturers as a part of a life cycle support agreement such as the Contractor Integrated Technical Information Services (CITIS). The functional (process) model developed by this project will provide electronics vendors a mapping to the different product development phases, in existence today, where the required product data is most cost effectively developed and captured. This mapping from the functional (process) model to the required data enables manufacturers to identify the best locations in their development processes for capturing the product data necessary for life cycle support. It is envisioned that the electronics CAD and tester manufacturers will, in time, develop tools and databases compatible with these standardized models. This will permit individual manufacturers to purchase commercially available tools which support the automated capture and use of standardized product data.

Demonstrations of the developed application protocols will be performed during PAP-E program phases 3 and 4 utilizing avionics modules targeted for next generation aircraft (See Figure 2). This rigorous test of the developed information models with complex electronics design, test, and diagnostics information and modified commercial CAD and tester tools will prove the accuracy of the developed models before submission to the standards processes. In addition, earlier CAD and tester application tool compatibility will be facilitated by this philosophy of early implementation and demonstration.

Figure 2. PAP-E Program Overview

STATUS

The PAP-E program entered Phase 2 of development in April 1992 (See Figure 2). During Phase 2 the information models, as developed, will be reviewed by industry experts. The industry experts will include electronics system developers, CAD suppliers, and tester vendors. Phase 2 will also involve the mapping of current electronics data standards into the information model to facilitate the acceptance and use of the developed information models by commercial CAD and tester vendors. The methodology for the use of the information model with current electronics data standards for the exchange of unambiguous, vendor independent information is shown in Figure 3. The application protocols planned for information modeling and demonstration are depicted in Figure 4. Additional industry and government review of the products of this program is welcome and invited.

Figure 3. Information Model Use for Data Exchange

Relationships with electronics standards bodies are in the process of being formalized. These close working relationships will include the IEEE, EIA, and CAD Framework Initiative (CFI). It is fundamental to the success of the program that current electronics data standards be utilized for the near term implementation of the information models to ensure uptake and acceptance by users and tool vendors.

Figure 4. Application Protocols Under Development

ABET Architecture Relationship

The PAP-E program relates to the ATLAS/Ada Based Environment for Test (ABET) architecture under development in the following ways. The ABET architecture calls for the definition of five information 'layers': Product Model Layer, Test Strategy and Requirements Layer, Test Procedure Layer, Test Resource Layer, and the Tester Bus Interface Layer (See Figure 5). The first two layers (e.g. Product Model and Test Strategy and Requirements) are product and test strategy information representation layers independent of specific design or test environments or methodologies. This is an important capability for ensuring the portability of information from design to test for initial test development, and also important for the re-targeting of design and test information to different environments for use during the life cycle of the product and/or associated test information. The capability to re-target is vital not only for test program set re-host, but also for the integration of complex electronics systems where design and test information exchange in an efficient and effective manner is paramount for successful development. The PAP-E information models under development are defining the product information which will populate much of the Product Model Layer of the ABET architecture. In addition, the PAP-E program will also demonstrate the use of product models defined by the Product Model Layer with test strategy and requirements languages defined in the ABET Test Strategy and Requirements Layer. This demonstration is intended to show the use of design and test environment independent information representation for use in performing simulation, test, and diagnostics in different companies, utilizing different design and test environments.

Figure 5. ABET Architecture

CONCLUSION

The development and demonstration of information necessary to provide life cycle support for complex electronics is of vital importance to electronics systems developers, supporters, and tool vendors. The PAP-E program described will provide valuable information and early CAD and tester tools from the program demonstrations. These developments will accelerate the exchange of unambiguous product information today using existing electronics data standards and also in the future with the use of PDES/STEP standard.